

AUTOMATED PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Abstract – Ensuring metadata compliance with the submission guidelines of preservation service providers is a labor-intensive process, requiring complex manual mapping and transformation. In this paper, we present a work-in-progress prototype for the automated preservation of digital objects from cultural heritage collections. To achieve this, we developed the Aggregator - a tool that manages preservation key functions such as SIP (Submission Information Packages) compilation, object upload, data integration, package handling, access control and client management. Designed for multi-client use, the system allows the preservation process to be entirely controlled by the client. As a result, no additional personnel resources are required from the digital preservation service provider for ingest, access, or package handling.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Why a solution for Cultural Heritage Collections?

Cultural heritage institutions in the German federal state of Brandenburg are typically non-profit or municipal organizations. Around 130 of them use the platform museum-digital.de for documentation and presentation within a regional instance, while the nationwide German platform includes approximately 1,150 institutions. As a multi-client system, it is a joint initiative of museums and their associations, incorporating metadata standards such as LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects) and authority files [1]. The platform also

provides access via API (application programming interface).

Although digital preservation should be a routine task, many institutions face limitations due to a lack of knowledge and resources [2]. Therefore, an ideal solution would be web-based, designed for multi-client use, pragmatic, easy to use and cost-effective. A concept for such a system was first published in 2017 [3]. A key priority for the community is ensuring that institutions retain custody of their data. By doing so, the system fosters a large-scale digital preservation network, laying the foundation for long-term sustainability.

Why an automated approach?

With the limited resources available, all information and digital objects required for the preservation process should be automatically collected from existing datasets or generated by the archival system itself. The key innovation of our approach lies in automated metadata and process handling, designed as a self-service solution. Assuming the integrity of the original data and files, this automation ensures a valid and reliable output.

The development of a prototype was made possible by leveraging the capabilities of relevant platforms and the latest versions of their APIs. We used sample metadata sets from museum-digital and digital copies of photo collections. However, the system is not restricted to this platform or image files in general.

II. ENTITIES AND FUNCTIONS OF AGGREGATOR

The Aggregator – our core management tool – was developed to be part of an OAIS (Open Archival Information System) with distributed functionality [4]. In our model, responsibilities are shared between two autonomous entities: the Aggregator and the Digital Depot. The system operates as a dark archive, granting access only to individual institutions (clients). Public access to cultural heritage is managed outside the preservation system through platforms such as museum-digital.de.

A. Entities

In line with our original concept [2], the system comprises three main entities, as shown in Figure 1.

- **Client:** Cultural heritage institutions act as producers of SIPs from their digital collections and as the sole consumers of their Archival Information Packages (AIP), which are generated and curated within the system.
- **Aggregator:** Service for SIP compilation, object upload, data aggregation and integration, package handling, access control, and overall client administration.
- **Digital Depot:** Service for preservation functions, including ingest, archival storage, and preservation planning.

Fig. 1 Aggregator functional entities and general data flow

B. Functions

The OAIS functions are distributed between the Aggregator and Digital Depot, as shown in Figure 1. The main functions include client identification, SIP compilation, ingest, data management, and access.

1) **Client Identification:** We use the International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organizations (ISIL) [5]. Institutional information is retrieved from the German ISIL Agency at the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin [6].

2) **Compilation of SIPs:** The process begins with the automated retrieval of metadata using the client's (producer) object ID from museum-digital.de via API. Next, associated primary files (e.g., master images) are uploaded from a local or cloud-based file system. Finally, SIPs are compiled automatically using BagIt [7]. Unlike other systems, no individual submission agreements between producers and the OAIS are required, as only standardized metadata and predefined processes are used. The system supports a single and multiple upload mode. While the single mode provides a detailed overview of the SIP content, the multiple mode automates the process further by enabling simultaneous file and dataset uploads via API. A dataset may contain a single file or multiple files (e.g., images).

3) The ingest process is managed through the connected ingest pipeline of the Digital Depot, designed as a self-service function that gives clients control within the Aggregator. The resulting AIPs include the original SIP, files converted to specified standards (if needed), and the Preservation Information Description (PID). For the prototype setting we use archivematica [8], an open-source digital preservation tool compliant with the OAIS functional model. Its latest API version enables a fully automated ingest process [9].

4) **Data-Management:** Includes processes for status tracking, package overview, and retrieval.

5) **Access:** A simple access functionality allows clients (consumer) to retrieve copies of their AIPs on demand. Data exchange is handled via the storage management system of the Digital Depot.

III. SIP-STRUCTURE AND METADATA

The compilation of SIPs is based on the BagIt tool and specification [7]. Object IDs correspond to the names of the main folders, with all associated files stored within these folders (1). The BagIt package (Figure 2) consists of the following components:

- **Data folder (11):** Contains SIP content information and digital objects (12) in various file formats.

- Metadata folder (7): Includes a METS file (8) describing the logical structure of the object and the contents of the data folder (11), a metadata file for the object (9), and a metadata file describing the institution (10).
- Package content information (2).
- BagIt version and tag code (3).
- Checksums for all files (4, 5).
- Readme file (6): Provides a description of the SIP structure and contents.
- Collection affiliation: The collection to which the object belongs.
- Inventory number: As assigned by the museum.
- Ingest status: Current processing state.
- AIP indicator: Symbol denoting the availability of an AIP.
- Error Log indicator: Symbol signaling the existence of an error logfile.

Fig. 2 STRUCTURE OF THE SUBMISSION INFORMATION PACKAGE

IV. DASHBOARD

The Aggregator features a simple dashboard (GUI) for managing packages (Figure 3). All essential metadata is stored in an internal database, with each dataset containing the following entries:

- Record ID: As used in museum-digital.de.
- Date/Time: Timestamp of data processing.
- Content indicator: Symbol representing the presence of digital content.
- Keywords: Terms for indexing and retrieval.
- Description: Detailed Object description.

To enhance search functionality, clicking the object symbol (6) displays the object's description along with a viewer. Clicking the AIP symbol (7) reveals the folder structure and contents, including a download function for on-demand access. The ingest status is visualized using the terms "processing," "complete," or "failed." In case of an error, the affected dataset is highlighted with a red background. Additionally, an error log file (8) is available for further analysis. The taskbar provides quick access to central functions:

- Institution Information (1): Displays details about the institution.
- Search (2): Allows searching for submitted packages.
- Start Archival Process (3): Initiates the archival workflow.
- Refresh AIP List (4): Updates the list of available AIPs.
- Online Help (5): Provides access to user support and documentation.

DE-MUS-055525 [Suche](#) [Objekt archivieren](#) [Aktualisieren](#) [Logout](#) [Hilfe](#) [Über](#)

① Durch Mausklick auf die **Objekt-Icons** werden Detailinformationen angezeigt.
 ① Mit **Aktualisieren** werden vorhandene **AIPs** angezeigt. Die Bereitstellung der **AIPs** kann einige Zeit in Anspruch nehmen.

Übersicht der bisherigen Ablieferungen
 Potsdam Museum - Forum für Kunst und Geschichte
 Es wurden insgesamt **3** Ablieferung(en) gefunden.

RecordID	Datum/Zeit	Objekt	Bezeichnung	Sammlung	Inventarnummer	Ingest	AIP	LOG
2702	2025-03-30 20:26:00							
2709	2025-03-30 20:27:01							
79757	2025-03-30 20:29:13		Blechspielzeug	Blechspielzeug	AK-2022-898	PROCESSING		

Fig. 3 DASHBOARD FOR SUBMISSION AND PACKAGE MANAGEMENT (SCREENSHOT)

V. CONCLUSION

Today's multi-client portals, such as museum-digital.de, use standardized object descriptions (e.g., LIDO for museums and related institutions). APIs provide structured access to this data and serve as an information source for automated archiving processes.

The Aggregator, as shown, is part of a prototype implementation of the OAIS concept with distributed functionality. It operates in a multi-client environment, leveraging standard metadata via API and tools with predefined processes and structures (e.g., BagIt) to generate automated, standardized SIPs without manual input. These SIPs are then automatically transformed into AIPs within the external Digital Depot, implemented in the prototype setting using archivematica. The Aggregator and Digital Depot are connected but not interdependent, meaning the preservation function can be provided by different vendors as a cloud service.

Our system functions as a self-service terminal, enabling clients to manage their data and packages. Core preservation tasks - ingest, storage management, and preservation planning - are handled by the Digital Depot. Splitting responsibilities between content management and standardized archiving results in a compact, pragmatic, and cost-effective solution.

By eliminating manual input, automated SIP compilation reduces errors. Clients require no specialized knowledge of digital archiving beyond content appraisal, as the self-service approach ensures seamless processing.

Successful automated archiving depends on several key factors, including metadata quality, APIs, and structured workflows. The value of AIPs relies entirely on the quality of the data and files. The more contextual information is included - via mandatory fields and metadata standards - the greater the long-term usefulness. Likewise, the selection of binary files (e.g., image formats) directly impacts digital preservation quality.

In our scenario, clients act as both producers and sole consumers of archival content within a dark archive multi-client system. Global access is managed outside the archival system through platforms such as museum-digital.de. Due to the dark archive concept, the OAIS access function can remain minimal.

The presented approach is adaptable for other communities and portals. Cloud systems offer the required connectivity and performance, while the use of metadata standards and structured descriptions enables standardized processing. A self-service model, combined with automated workflows, minimizes the need for extensive training or specialized expertise. Implementing such digital preservation services could mean that even small cultural heritage institutions have a real chance to take on the digital preservation task.

REFERENCES

- [1] Museum-digital. <https://www.museum-digital.de/en.htm>
- [2] Preuss, U. Sustainable Digitalization of Cultural Heritage - Report on Initiatives and Projects in Brandenburg, Germany. In: Sustainability 2016, 8(9), 891. Basel. MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090891>
- [3] Daessler, Rolf; Preuss, Ulf. Digital preservation of cultural heritage for small institutions. In: Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Digital Preservation, Boston, MA, USA, 24. - 27. September 2018. <https://osf.io/52cs7/>
- [4] CCSDS. Recommended practice for an OAIS reference model. CCSDS 650.0-M-3. Dec. 2024. <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m3.pdf>
- [5] [03] ISO 15511:2019. Information and documentation -- International standard identifier for libraries and related organizations (ISIL). <https://www.iso.org/standard/77849.html>
- [6] German ISIL-Agency. Format of address records. <https://isil.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/vergabe/adressenformat>
- [7] RFC 8493. The BagIt File Packaging Format (V1.0). Oct. 2018. <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc8493>
- [8] Artefactual. Archivematica. <https://www.archivematica.org/en/>
- [9] Artefactual. Archivematica API. <https://www.archivematica.org/en/docs/archivematica-1.17/dev-manual/api/api-reference-archivematica/>

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